

Diction: A Panacea For National Integration In Nigeria

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Abstract

Speech is the vocalized form of communication used by human and some animals, which is based upon the syntactic combination of items drawn from the lexicon. It could be in form of trance, conversation, address etc. it could also be argumentative, persuasive, descriptive etc. Diction is a style of speaking or writing as dependent upon choice of words. Individuals vary their diction depending on different contexts and settings. It may be “formal” where words are used in formal situations e.g press, conference, presentations etc. similarly we use “informal diction” in informal situations like writing or talking to our friends. Moreover, a colloquial diction uses words common in every day speech. National integration is the awareness of a common identity amongst the citizens of a country. We must fight the good fight of nation building and together we must show how patriotic we are as a people. This paper discusses the use of diction in speech to achieve the much-desired national integration. For the purpose of clarity, there were conceptual study and theoretical framework. There were textual analysis and recommendations were also put forward to help achieve the objective of this paper.

Key words: Speech, Diction, National Integration, peace, communication Accommodation.

Introduction

Speech is the spoken form of language which is at the heart of all things human. O’ Grady, Archibald and Katamba (2011:1) posit that: “Language is at the heart of all things Human. We use it when we are talking”.

Thinking, reading, writing and listening, are all part of the social structure of diverse communities. Speech forges the emotional bond between

parent and child; it is the vehicle for literature and poetry.

Language is a coded structure by which human beings communicate. It is part of the human structure or attribute and so exist in the environment of human beings and not outside it. It is part of the human social structure. Language is not just a part of us but it defines us, by bringing out the totality of us in terms of

expression. Carnie (2007:4) upholds that “Language is that part of the mind that allows us to speak . One thing that distinguishes us from other animals or relatively smart one like the chimps and elephant is the ability to use combinatory language”. Little wonder they say; “no language, no man” Language has an unending advantage if we begin to recount its benefits to man and the whole world at large; we may run into endless beginnings. However, languages with its numerous advantages can be used to do any business depending on the interlocutors. It can destroy as well as join or bring people together.

In a multi ethnic and multi lingual society such as Nigeria where there are people with diverse cultures, and belief systems, language can be used to integrate the people by concatenation and bringing their ideas and believes together through their choice of election which in other words brings about mutual intelligibility and peace paramount amongst the objectives of this paper are;

1. How to do things with words
2. Language and national unity
3. To bring the people together through language
4. To use language to ward off segregation amongst Nigerians etc.

Speech is a formal talk that a person gives to an audience each spoken word is created of the phonetic combination of a limited set of vowel and consonant speech sound unit (Phonemes).

One distinguishing feature of speech is that it employs some paralinguistic features such as gesture and facial expression speech can be synonymous to lecture, address, talk, sermon, etc. It can be in form of narrative, descriptive, argumentative etc. Depend on its purpose. When the purpose of speech is for peace and friendship, one can employ diction.

According to Wikipedia: Diction refers to the speakers distinctive vocabulary choice and style of expression it referees chiefly to the choice of words, their arrangement and the force , accuracy and distinction with which they are used.

A secondary common meaning of diction is the distinction between speech and the art of speaking so that each word is clearly heard and understood to its fullest complexity and extremity as it concerns pronunciation and tone rather than word choice and style. This secondary sense is more precisely and commonly expressed with the term enunciation or with its synonym articulation.

Diction is defined as the degree of clarity and distinctiveness of pronunciation in speech. One of the biggest frustration in communication is the inability to understand what a person is saying.

This can lead to even a heated argument, family disputes and lover's quarrels.

Diction or styles of writing often separates good writing from bad writing. It depends on a number of factors proper diction is important to get the messages across. Diction is usually judged with reference to prevailing standards of proper writing and speech and it is seen as the mark of quality of writing.

National integration is the awareness of a common identity amongst the citizens of a country. It means that though we belong to different states, religions and speak different languages; we recognize the fact that we are all one. This kind of integration is very important in the building of a strong and prosperous nation.

Unity in our country does not mean the kind of oneness that comes from racial and cultural similarity. It is unity in spite of great differences in other words, unity in diversity. An important historical event in which this unity was displayed was the freedom movement when all Nigerians united against the British Rule.

Nigeria is the largest country in Africa unique features one of our country is unique feature that all the major religions of the world are practiced here in our country like traditional, Islamic, Christianity, Buddhism etc. There are also great varieties, and social customs. Geographically, our land is diverse and there are amazing

differences in climate. Despite all these difference Nigeria is a political entity, every part of which is governed under the same constitution. We have to co-exist with each other peacefully; respect the culture and religion of our fellow Nigerians. With this in place, national integration can be achieved.

Conceptual Framework

Speech

Speech is the vocalized form of communication used by humans. It is based upon the syntactic combination of words and meaning. There are deferent types of speech: Expository, Analytical, Speech of introductions, Speech of Presentations Speech of Acceptance, Commemorative, Speech, After Dinner Speech, Persuasive Speech and Inspirational Speech.

Diction

Diction is style of speaking or writing as dependent upon choice of words. It refers chiefly to the choice of words, and their arrangement, the force, accuracy and distinction with which they are used. The choice of words with regard to correctness, clarity and effectiveness. The accent, inflection, intonation and speech sound quality manifested by an individual speaker, usually judged in terms of prevailing standards of acceptability enunciation.

National Integration

National integration is a process of creating a sense of national consciousness, uniqueness of identity and loyalty among people with different social cultural identities, racial, ethnic, language, religions etc. into a single territorial political society. National integration is the key to the realizations of unity peace and progress in the entire nation

Peace: Peace is freedom from disturbance. It is a state of tranquility, harmony and order. Peace is lack of conflict and freedom from fear of violence between heterogeneous social groups. Peace denotes situation or a period of time in which there is no war or violence in a country or an area. (Oxford Advanced Learners dictionary 7th edition).

Communication: according to Awoniyi (1982:2) is the means by which we pass from one person to another our ideas, feelings, our knowledge, our requests indeed, every aspect of human life. Ngonebu (2008:1) defined communication as any transmission of information from one person to another in order to elicit a response.

Theoretical Framework

Theory 1: Peace Studies

Peace studies by John Galtung (1996) the father of peace studies. Peace studies can be classified as multidisciplinary, encompassing elements of

politics and international relations (particularly critical international relations theory) sociology, psychology, Anthropology and economics critical theory is also widely used in peace and conflict studies. It entails understanding the concept of peace which is defined as political condition that stabilizes through formal and informal institutional practices and norms.

Johnian Galtung(1996) identified two aspects of peace positive and negative peace. In positive peace Galtung described as peace with justices for all. Often times “Peace” as absence of some negative force such as tension or violence; It is also the presence of justice. We often times use unjust methods to create a false sense of peace. Positive peace is a true, lasting and sustainable peace built on justice for all peoples. In Negative peace for instance when a ceasefire is enacted, a negative peace will ensure, it is negative because something undesirable has stopped happening (E.g violence stopped, the oppression ended).

Negative peace is therefore seen as peace without justice. It is a false sense of peace that often comes at the expense of justice. In negative peace situations, you may not see conflict out in the open but the tension is boiling just beneath the surface because the conflict was never reconciled.

Positive peace is filled with lots of positive contents such as restoration of relationships, the

creation of social system that serve the needs of the whole population and the constructive resolution of conflict.

Peace does not mean the total absence of violence in all forms and the unfolding of conflict in a constructive way. Peace therefore exist where people are interacting non violently and are managing their conflict positively with respectful attention to the legitimate needs and interest of all concerned.

One can make effort to achieve negative peace as it is in Nigeria today by managing interpersonal and organizational conflict in order to control, contain and reduce actual and potential violence. Reducing the incidence of war by eliminating the extreme dangers of the war system or limiting war through international crisis management one can also plan to prevent war through strategic deterrence and arms control.

Positive peace is the only way out of the Nigerian present situation. Thus, peace which is more than absence of violence rather peace that has the presence of social justice through equal opportunity, a fair distribution of power and resources, equal protection of lives and properties as well as impartial enforcement of law.

Positive peace therefore exists where people are managing their conflict positively with respectful

attention to the legitimate needs and interest of all concerned.

Grewal (2003) asserts that the word peace is the central focus in conflict resolution. The peace process will utilize words phrases and sentences that are not offensive. Thus, the expanded definition of violence led to the expanded definition of peace” p.1 since peace does not just mean the absence of war, abuses, actions and inactions also threaten peace. The theory posits that “negative peace is the absence of violence, absence of war”, “and positive peace is the integration of human society”. If we reflect on altercations in politics and number of them threaten the peace of the country, the expanded concept of peace and violence.

We have an interwoven concept of peace, violence and national development. The social concept of mutual respect is an ingredience of peace. Abuse of due process threatens peace, individual abuse is inimical to peace. Any form of injustice is an aberration of the peace process. It is often said that injury to one is injury to all.

Theory 2

Theory (CAT) is a communication developed by Howard Giles Santa Barbara in 1991. It argues that, when people interact they adjust their speech their vocal patterns and their gestures, to accommodate others the theory explores the various reasons why individuals emphasize or m

the social differences between themselves and their interlocutors (a person taking part in a conversation with you) through verbal and non verbal communication.

This theory is concerned with the links between language, context and identity. It focuses on both the intergroup and interpersonal factors that lead to accommodation, as well as the ways that power, macro and micro-context concerns affect communication behaviours. This theory describes two main accommodation processes “convergence which refers to strategies through which individual adapt to each other’s communication behaviours to reduce these social differences between themselves and their interlocutors. Sometimes when individuals try to engage in convergence. They can also end up over accommodating and despite their intentions their convergence can be seen as condescending.

This theory evolved from the speech accommodation theory (SAT) but has been traced back to Giles account mobility model of 1973. The speech accommodation theory was developed to demonstrate the values of social psychological concepts to understanding the dynamics of speech. It sought to explain –the motivations underlying certain shifts in people’s speech styles during social consequences arising from them, particularly, it focused on the cognitive and effective processes underlying

individuals convergence and divergence through speech. This theory has been broadened to include not only speech but also the non-verbal and discursive dimensions of social interaction. Thus, it now encompasses other aspects of communication. In addition CAT has moved in a more inter-disciplinary direction than the previous speech accommodation theory. It now also covers a wider range of phenomena

There are also four major assumptions under which this theory is based. These are:

- There are speech and behavioural similarities and dissimilarities in all conversations.
- The way we perceive the speech and behaviours of another determine our evaluation of the conversation.
- Language and behaviours have the ability to communicate social status and group belonging between people in a conversation.
- Norms guide the accommodation process, which varies in its degree of appropriateness

There are so many factors that make people accommodate others, these are age, sex. Academic qualification, culture, status, religious denomination and others. How do Speakers Accommodate Others?

According to Wardhaugh speakers accommodate interlocutors in the following ways:

1. When you respond to and develop a topic introduced by your addressee, you are converging in the content of the speech of the addressees,
2. When people simplify their vocabulary and grammar while talking to foreigners or children, they are converging downwards. Towards the lesser linguistic proficiency of their addressees.
3. When a complicated technical message is translated for the benefit of someone who does not know⁷ the jargon, speech accommodation is involved.
4. When someone adopts the pronunciation of another person higher in rank or academics, the person is converging upward in his speech.
5. When a person chooses a variety of language that is most comfortable for his addressees, the person is being accommodative.
6. In the market place, people sometimes accommodate to the language of the person selling goods in order to secure goodwill and hopefully, a good bargain,
7. When people codeswitch they are being accommodative. He further adds that by code-switching in a conversation a speaker can both access different identities and accommodate to meet someone else half-way, establish common ground and show flexibility and openness (Wardhaugh 11.5).

Textual Analysis

If we consider this newspaper headline:

86 killed as herdsmen attack 11 plateau villages
SDC injured, 50 house burnt plateau places three
LGAs under curfew.

Punch June 25, p1.

This newspaper headline is enough to start off a conflict between the people and herdsmen. This newspaper banner is written in such a way that offences are aroused. The figures are written in Arabic numerals (86) not in words so that sensibility of the reader will be offender. In a community where 80 people have been killed certainly peace has been threatened and the people's anger aroused. If the killing had been done by unknown persons it is a different ball game from giving the names of the killers in this regards herdsmen. Suffice it to say that the state of Plateau was besieged and people murdered in cold blood. As one would expect the people took to the streets and even besieged the government house. The government on its part placed the LGAs under curfew.

This text by Goodluck Jonathan is in a pensive mood which is adumbrated by the word "Reflection" He talks of "mindset" which again points to both attitude, perception and reflection.

As president his speech bothers on "National integration" no president would want the nation to disintegrate under his watch hence the occurrence of such words such as "Unity, faith, peace and progress" most other such lexical

items. He evokes the constitution which is the mainstay of any president in this speech, the “1999 Constitution”, is given a pride of place. This speech has the ambience of a political treatise and a “ground, norm for the nation’s existence” lexical items such as constitution, constitutional Provisions, National Objectives, are rife to the extent that they accommodate all people in the country. A presidential speech is one that must reassure the citizenry of the protection of their lives and property. It must be couched in such a way that every citizen will feel protected provided for and accommodated hence the choice of the accommodationist theory for this work is apt and linguistically justified in the analysis of this treatise for instance the president writes, “every citizen in all parts of the Federation...” The nation has moved from militancy to terrorism in fifteen years”

The citations above, express concern over the continued existence of the nation as one indivisible entity. The authority of government is expressed in words such as:

- The Federal government
- Promulgate residential requirement
- Discharging your full legal and civic responsibilities

We note with passion, words such as discharging which is an inkling that citizens must perform some roles. They are not to be dormant, they

must be seen as players in the national polity. Their roles are broadly divided into two parts, the Legal and Civic a breach of these roles may lead to some measures being leveled against the citizen. He reiterates “This is what happens in other nations.

This text is an excerpt from Miyetti Allah which is an umbrella name cum organization in Nigeria. “There would be more violence if the anti-grazing laws were not repealed daily sun Feb 6, 2018.

The call by the leader of Miyeti Allah is defiant. It rebuffs the Benue state ant-grazing law. The leaders of Miyeti Allah by the use of the word violence. It is not only that there will be violence but more violence leaders of Miyetti Allah dances the government and are ready to match force with force. It sets up a parallel government contrary to that of the Benue state government. The state enacted a law and Miyetti Allah wants the law repealed. We limit ourselves to the linguistic import of the speech looking such as words that x-ray the meaning of the speaker. For Miyetti, the Anti-grazing law is offensive. Linguistically we know that the prefix anti- is repulsive, it gives us the stance of defiance, opposition, negation and all other contrary connotations. The root word, grazing is usually positive relating to the feeding which for the most part, leads to nourishment

Recommendations

- Promotion of Cultural Re-orientation Awareness: This can be done by strengthening the national orientation agency (NOA) to encourage Nigerians to learn the languages, eat the food and wear the traditional dresses of one another
- Encouraging inter-ethnic and inter-tribal marriages: This helps in promoting national Unity. Through this, cultural ties are strengthened among Nigerians.
- Encouraging Nigerians to be patriotic :The people must all feel as Nigerians with one destiny and one goal they must, have “We” feeling.
- Organizing National Cultural Festival: This brings people of different cultural, religions, class etc. together. This will help people to understand and appreciate other people’s culture
- Promoting equal economic opportunity: There must be conscious effort to promote equal economic opportunities for all social cultural groups in Nigeria.
- **Providing Equal Access to Education:** Equal Education opportunities should be given to all Nigerians from primary to tertiary levels.
- **Promoting Public Education for National Integration:** This can be done through the mass media by sensitizing Nigerians on common national issues and values.
- **Providing equal access to representation in government:** The application of federal character of quota principle in appointment into positions in government at all levels will help achieve equal access to representation.
- **Strengthening the National Youth Service corps (NYSC) Scheme:** More incentives such as automatic employment, cash donations, awards etc. should be given to outstanding corps members who served in other states outside their cultural areas.
- Promoting Religions Tolerance citizens should respect one another’s religion.
- There should be good and responsible governance / leadership to promote sense of belonging among Nigerians
- Formation of a Political Party with National Outlook. Political parties should assume national character. Parties should have their Headquarters in the Federal Capital. It must also accept people from all walks of life to be members.
- Adoption of an Indigenous Language as an Official National Language (lingua franca) if all the above should be implemented then national integration can be easily achieved.

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